

REPORT:

A1.4.1: Review on Hydrogen Refuelling Station Parameters used in particulate Sampling

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Confidentiality: Public

Submission date: 29.07.2024

Revision: -

<https://www.ri.se/en/methytrucks>

A1.4.1. Review on Hydrogen Refuelling Station Parameters Used in Direct Gas Sampling.	
Funding European Metrology Partnership	Grant agreement no: 22NRM03
Project name Metrology to support standardisation of hydrogen fuel sampling for HD	Project short name MethyTruck
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<p>Summary</p> <p>The decarbonisation of the transportation sector is crucial for meeting net-zero targets. Fuel Cell Electric Vehicles (FCEVs) running on hydrogen offer a promising solution, with hydrogen quality being critical for FCEV performance. The aim is to review current state-of-the-art hydrogen sampling parameters for particulate, identify patterns, and propose a more accurate and representative approach for standardisation while minimising hazards. The study involved a comprehensive state-of-the-art review on the parameters used for hydrogen particulate sampling.</p> <p>The findings provide detailed insights into each parameter, identifying trends in parameter configuration, including pressure, venting, flow rate, and temperature. The outcome of this work revealed the overtly unstandardised nature of the hydrogen sampling process. State-of-the-art reviews also provide knowledge of hydrogen sampling, insights into possibly establishing an internationally accepted, efficient, and safe method, and help transition towards a decarbonised transportation sector.</p>	
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Contents

Introduction	3
Particulate sampling strategies review	3
Hydrogen mass metering	4
Minimum hydrogen mass	5
Filter type	6
HD particulate sampling hardware	6
Expert feedback	7
Conclusion	8
References	10

Introduction

The transportation sector's decarbonisation is crucial for meeting Europe's net-zero targets. Fuel Cell Electric Vehicles (FCEVs) provide a promising solution for transportation decarbonisation as they generate electricity using hydrogen fuel cells to power the electrical engine, emit only water and heat [1]. Hydrogen quality is critical for FCEV performance and durability [2]. The international standard ISO 14687:2019 [3] and European standard EN 17124:2022 [4] set limits for 15 contaminants in the hydrogen matrix. Two main methods for analysing hydrogen are online and offline analysis, as outlined in ISO 19880-8 [5]. Despite development of online and offline analysis method for gas compounds, particulate analysis presents several challenges. Online analysis, defined as the real-time measurement of particulate in hydrogen fuel, would be extremely interesting but there is no current solution to achieve it within the extreme condition of a hydrogen refuelling station (pressure ramping up to 70 MPa, temperature from -40 degree Celsius up to 85 degrees Celsius, and high flow up to 120 g/s). On the other hand, offline analysis offers the advantage of using a state-of-the-art analytical laboratory equipment (e.g., high precision balance able to accurately determine the particulate mass on a filter exposed to a few hundred grams to kilograms of hydrogen). Offline analysis for particulates requires a four-step process of capturing, storing, transporting and analysing hydrogen purity in an offsite laboratory. The current study focuses on the sampling and particulate mass measurement in hydrogen fuel using filter.

Direct particulate sampling can be performed using two methodologies which either involve using the HD-HRS in maintenance mode, or in a normal refuelling event, where a particulate filter is placed in between the HD-HRS and the FCEV.

A recent study from Aarhaug et al. [6] identified the two strategies, the sampling systems associated and their characteristics. This report will use the results of this study realised in 2024 and the recent standard ASTM D7650-21 [7].

The aim of this task is to evaluate the impact of the HD-HRS's operational parameters on direct particulate sampling. This will include special consideration of the impact of pressure and flow on particulate collection and flow metering. Flow metering metrology is critical in providing the final measurement of the particulate mass fraction in mg per kg of hydrogen.

Particulate sampling strategies review

As reviewed by Aarhaug et al. [6] and ASTM D7650-21 [7], two sampling approaches are currently used called:

- “atmosphere approach” (i.e., Airborne MRM-7650)
- “tank approach” (i.e., HYDAC).

The two approaches diverge in their realisation. The “tank approach” will operate during a FCEV refuelling with the filter in between the HRS and the FCEV. The realisation may follow the normal filling protocol. In this case, the pressure, temperature, or flow rate may not be controlled. The atmosphere approach will operate with the station in maintenance mode, the pressure, temperature, and flow can then be specified, however there is no recommendation on the conditions to apply in the ASTM D7650 standards. A challenge with the atmosphere approach is the actual venting of the hydrogen at flow rate of several gram per second for a period of several minutes, which requires appropriate venting system and approval.

Currently the impact of pressure or flow rate is not well understood. The impact of temperature may be important as the presence of water may lead to a different outcome at ambient temperature (gaseous) compared to -40 °C (solid) as explained by Aarhaug et al. [6]. Based on the current knowledge, the pressure and flow rate need to be investigated in dynamic and static mode while understanding the difference of results between ambient and -40 °C. Hydrogen fuelling in presence of water may be another interesting aspect that may have an impact on the determination of particulates in hydrogen.

Other important aspects of the particulate measurement are the actual filter (mass and type) and hydrogen mass measurement. Recent metrology projects (16ENG01 and 19ENG04) highlighted the challenges around the type of filter, cleaning, and handling to achieve an accurate measurement. The actual hydrogen mass measurement is critical to the overall measurement in mg/kg and how it is achieved and traceable is important. These aspects will be discussed in the next sections.

Hydrogen mass metering

Hydrogen mass metering is essential in the particulate measurement as it will define the actual mass of hydrogen corresponding to the mass of particulate on the filter. Inaccuracy in the measurement would lead to biased results.

Following the different approaches, several options for measuring the mass of hydrogen passing through the filter can be performed:

- using the HRS recording of the hydrogen delivered to the vehicle (upstream measurement), the mass obtained will be traceable to the HRS flow meters and to their uncertainties. It would be important to ensure that the HRS flow meter is calibrated and verified according to OIML R139
- using the volume, temperature, and pressure of the tank only for the Tank approach. This methodology relies on being able to access this information from a vehicle or a

tank reservoir and the sensors should be calibrated and verified with associated uncertainty.

- using a Coriolis flow meter or a secondary mass flow meter standard after the filter holder to measure accurately and independently the hydrogen mass passing through the filter. In case a low uncertainty is required, the use of hydrogen flow primary standard developed by national metrology institute [8] would provide the lowest uncertainty.

The three approaches require different infrastructure, and the traceability chain is slightly different when relying on the mass flow meter of the HRS (dependence on third party). Ensuring the flow measurement is part of the particulate sampling system would allow a better traceability and control over the measurement. An evaluation of the different approaches and the uncertainty associated would be important to advice on the most relevant approach for the industry.

Minimum hydrogen mass

A point to address is the required amount of hydrogen gas required to achieve the measurement of particulate. As the particulate amount fraction is set at 1 mg/kg, an hydrogen mass of 1 kg would represent 20% of the full refill of a light duty FCEV (considering a tank of 5kg). In this case, the sampled gas represents 20% of the complete gas reaching the FCEV, however in the case of a bus or a truck, 1 kg only represents less than 5% of the complete gas reaching the vehicle. An important parameter is to understand how the sample taken would represent the overall population. Two considerations can be made, the population is the complete hydrogen refilled (LD FCEV: 4-5 kg and HD FCEV: 20-80kg) or it is the HRS delivery over a year. In each case, it is important to understand how the subsample taken would represent the two potential populations. It may be done following few routes:

- realise repetitive quartering of the complete refill: consider the complete refill mass and realise repetitive sampling at different time (i.e., sampling 1 kg at beginning, sampling 1kg in middle, sampling 1 kg at end) and compare to a complete sampling of the full refill. The study can be repeated few times to increase number of point and help define if subsample is appropriate and representative. In a recent ISO/PRF 19880-9, a value of 2.5 kg is provided without clear technical evidence.
- define sampling plan to determine if one FCEV refuelling sampling is representative. This may be done by repetitive sampling at different time of the same HRS to determine variation over time and sampling realisation. Duplicate sampling (2 independent sampling at similar time) could help to determine particulate sampling uncertainty.

Some technical challenges arise to realise it in field (i.e., need of changing filter in field, conservation of filter outside housing).

Currently the minimum mass to sample, the subsample definition and the number of replicates are not sufficiently studied to determine the optimal minimum sample mass for particulate sampling. The recommendation would be to sample the complete FCEV refill equivalent to 4 to 5 kg of hydrogen fuel for a light duty and more than 20 kg for a heavy duty.

Filter type

The filters used for particulate determination varies in pore diameter between 0.2 μm and 5 μm . A recent study [9] showed no major difference in filtration efficiency of 300 nm particulate between 0.2 and 5 μm filter pore diameter. Therefore, other parameters may be important to define the most relevant filter type: behaviour in measurement condition (e.g., loss of mass, resistance to impact). Aarhaug et al. [6] reported several observations from experts: pressure impact on the filter (e.g., visible mark on filter after sampling), penetration or pinhole observed by microscopy. Moreover, they reported the measurement of negative mass after filter weighing which could be related to pressure impact on the filter, mass of hydrogen sampled, transportation, delay, and condition of analysis. During the filter transportation from field site to laboratory, vibration and manipulation could lead to particulate loss especially at such low amount fraction (hundreds of μg).

Different approaches for the determination of the hydrogen mass may be realised and as highlighted by Aarhaug et al. [6], the lack of standardisation in filter type, and balance requirement need to be addressed. Most North America systems use 0.2 μm pore size 47 mm PTFE (ASTM D7650) whereas in Europe, 5.0 μm pore size 47 mm PTFE filters are used per manufacturer requirement (HYDAC).

The new challenges associated with heavy-duty will be handling the higher flow rate and the potential impact on the filter. It is essential that the integrity of the filter is maintained, as mass loss due to flow would lead to negative value and underestimation of the real mass amount.

HD particulate sampling hardware

A review of the industry's best practices was carried out and only one sampling system was compatible with the highest flow rate obtained for heavy duty. Due to the lack of measurement system, it may be considered to realise the particulate measurement at lower flow condition (up to 60 g/s). An assumption should be made that flow rate from 60 g/s to 120 g/s would not impact significantly the particulate mass.

For the light duty particulate sampling, three systems are commercially available: PSA-H70 and HYDAC MK2 (HYDAC) and MRM-7650 (Airborne laboratories). Other non-commercial systems are in use worldwide.

Table 1. Summary of particulate sampling system available in 2023

Use/Application	Light-Duty sampler	Light-Duty sampler	Light-Duty sampler	Heavy-Duty sampler
Sampling system	PSA-H70	HYDAC MK2	MRM-7650	Hy-Strainer T1050
Manufacturer or reference	HYDAC ASTM D7650-13 ISO 19880-1 Annex K	HYDAC ASTM D760-21 ISO 19880-1 Annex K	Airborne laboratories ASTM D7650-21	EV Metalværk A/S for Boyd Hydrogen/NEL
Commercially available	Outdated, replaced by HYDAC MK2	yes	yes	yes
Vent	FCEV sink	FCEV sink	Atmospheric vent system	Vent to atmosphere/ vehicle/simulated tank
Hydrogen metering	Recording of the HRS dispenser meter	Recording of the HRS dispenser meter	Coriolis mass flow meter with cumulative flow	Recording of the HRS dispenser meter
Filter type available	HahneMuhle PT 020 47 BL (Ø47mm; 0.2 µm pore size)	Millipore Mitex LSWP04700 (Ø47mm; 5.0 µm pore size)	Pall TF-200 (Ø47mm; 0.2 µm pore size)	Ø47mm test chamber

For the “tank approach” or FCEV sink as defined in Table 1, the overall parameters follow the filling protocol. For the atmosphere approach, MRM-7650 requires the HRS in maintenance mode, pressure of 413 bar and 20 g/s flow rate. These conditions could be requested at an HD-HRS. Using this equipment would allow to study the impact of several HRS parameters on particulate mass measurements.

This report identifies the need for the development of new high flow particulate sampling system, and potentially to investigate alternative measurement approaches (e.g., a Tapered Element Oscillating Microbalance). Following the development of new particulate sampling technologies for high flow rate (60 g/s to 120 g/s even 300 g/s), future studies will be required to verify the assumption made on the flow impact on particulate mass measurement and develop a better understanding of particulate mass at high flow rate.

Expert feedback

Most particulate samplings are realised using the “tank approach” worldwide. Several experts in hydrogen sampling were contacted and they highlighted they found water on filters when sampling at -40°C.

Figure 1. Example of water and oil on filter

Another point is the risk of negative weight in the situation of elevated water amount fraction and high flow which create the condition of fast iced moisture puncturing the filter.

The development of particulate measurement is often challenging due to the unavailability of reference standard or HRS with measurable amount of particulate to allow method validation.

Particulate measurement is still a challenging realisation for light duty application and the implementation at heavy duty is adding complexity due to the high flow, lack of equipment and the difficulty to find a reliable location to perform testing (with measurable particulate).

Conclusion

Based on the report, several challenges were identified:

- lack of hardware to measure particulate at high flow conditions required for heavy-duty. Most commercial particulate sampling system are designed for flow up to 60 g/s. Further development is needed for high flow particulate sampling;
- Particulate mass sampling using HRS in manual mode (e.g., flow reduction below 60 g/s, use of particulate sampling system without a sink or a tank). It is often difficult in the field to have technical staff able to control the HRS parameters, it requires planning and involvement of the HRS operators. An option would be to operate the sampling at light duty condition if it is demonstrated that the actual flow has no direct impact on the measurement.

The parameters that influence the results were reviewed:

- hydrogen mass metering is critical and not standardised. Discussion may be required to ensure the traceability of the results when using the HRS flow meter. The actual uncertainty of the hydrogen mass may be compared based on the different approaches available. Recommendation can be proposed based on the impact of the hydrogen

mass metering realised (i.e., HRS metering, Coriolis flow meter as part of the system, additional metering system as secondary standard);

- standardisation of the filter type (0.2 or 5.0 μm) especially for heavy duty, high flow applications. It may be important to ensure the suitability of the filter for high flow conditions and to study any degradation (i.e., mass loss, puncture) when increasing flow and pressure.

The HRS parameters that may be critical to compare:

- pressure and filling protocol, it would be interesting to compare sampling using “tank approach” against “atmosphere approach” at different pressures (i.e., 20, 100, 350 and 415 bar);
- flow and filling protocol, it would be interesting to compare sampling using “tank approach” against “atmosphere approach” (fixed pressure: 415 bar) at different flow rates (i.e., 10, 30, 60 and 120 g/s if technically possible);
- impact of water amount fraction: comparison of precooled hydrogen and ambient to determine if ice formation impacts the filter and the mass realisation.

Future work may compare sample representativeness after applying stated parameters and procedures after the study of the above-mentioned criteria. Standardisation of particulate sampling parameters is crucial to ensure the consistency and reliability of results obtained from hydrogen sampling in HRS. Developing a globally accepted hydrogen sampling method is necessary to promote safety, accuracy, and efficiency in the field. This report offers valuable insights for stakeholders in hydrogen sampling. It serves as a starting point for future research and development in this area with the objective of advancing the use of hydrogen as a clean and sustainable energy source.

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